

VALUE BASED EDUCATION: A PASSAGE TO UNIVERSAL PEACE

Dr. Kallave Maheshwar Gangadharrao

Assistant Professor

Department of Education,

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada

University, Sub Campus-Osmanabad

Abstract

Value Based Education is important to help everyone in improving the value system that he/she holds and put them to use. Once, we understand our values in life, we can examine and control the various choices we make in our lives. It's our duty to uphold the various types of values in life such as cultural values, universal values, personal values and social values. Thus, value based education is always essential to shape a student's life and to give him an opportunity of performing himself on the global stage. The need for value based education among the parents, children, teachers etc, is constantly increasing as we continue to witness increasing violent activities, behavioral disorder and lack of unity in society.

Key Words: Value, Education, Universal Peace, Teaching, Curriculum, Activities

Introduction:

education is power

Value based education (VBE) is not a dead process. It is lively dynamic bipolar process of transformation. According to this view, there must be two poles for its operation – the one is the Teacher and other is child as student. The teacher possesses some belief, ideals and values and these influence the child. In other words, we can say that the teacher is a philosopher, who tries to mould and develop the child according to his philosophy to attain a desirable type of individual.

Value Based Education is really the process of removing the ignorance that is covering our inner knowledge, which is absolute, which is perfect, which is eternal, which is supreme.

Objectives of Value Based Education

1. To provide them successful experiences in solving those problems. Here and now and thus preparing them to solve future problem.
2. To provide them experiences leading them to become better citizens in a democracy.
3. To provide students opportunities for the maximum self-realization.
4. To develop a well-integrated personality of the student with which he may be able, to adjust himself and to improve the social and physical environment in active cooperation with others.

Difference between Formal Education (FE) & Value Based Education (VBE)

Sr. No.	Formal Education (FE)	Value Based Education (VBE)
01	FE opens up our mind	VBE gives us purity of heart
02	FE provides us with skills	VBE provides us sincerity
03	FE extends our relationship with the world	VBE links us with our own family members
04	FE makes our living better	VBE makes our life better
05	FE teaches us to compete with others	VBE encourages us to be complete
06	FE makes us a good professional	VBE makes us a whole human
07	FE takes us to the top	VBE takes the whole society to the top

08	FE gives us capacity of better learning	VBE gives us the tool for a deeper understanding
09	FE gives us only food	VBE provides us appetite with food
10	FE may bring limitations	VBE is for liberation

Importance of Value Based Education:

The realization of VBE has become quite strong in last few decades on a global level. The negative forces like selfishness, hatred, terrorism, individualism, violence, intolerance, etc. have now become day-to-day problems in the world. The phenomena such as family breakdown, increasing of negative attitude and spread of health hazards like drugs and HIV/AIDS seem to be escalating worldwide, which have now terrified humanity. These are, of course, very threatening challenges to the peaceful existence of humankind.

Values Coming from within	Being Practiced
1. Love 2. Kindness 3. Compassion 4. Mercy 5. Sympathy 6. Empathy	1. Punctuality 2. Discipline 3. Obedience 4. Behavior 5. Conduct 6. Character

Value Based Education will help:

Sr. No.	Component	Description
01	Need to Understand Oneself	a) Who Am I? b) What is my goal? c) How should I proceed towards my goal?
02	Management of Self	a) Time Management b) Stress Management c) Life Management
03	Decision Making	a) What is good for me? b) How to make decisions? c) Co-operation and Co-ordination
04	Personality Development	a) What is Personality? b) How should one develop personality? c) How should I mould myself? d) Facing situations

Content of Value Based Education Curriculum:

1. It includes the individual in relation to family, contribution of individual member, mutual help, respect and cooperation, right and obligations of children and parents, family as a cradle of social and civic virtues.
2. It includes personal hygiene, good manner, religious and social customs.
3. It involves human relationships expanding to social orders.
4. It discussed how man satisfies his basic needs.
5. It is the discussion of science in the service of man.

Inculcate value through curricular activities & Role of Teacher:

Due to liberalization, industrialization and globalization rapid changes are occurring in almost all social sciences. The value possessed and their attitudes according to the changes should be known up to date vast changes are occurring in the education. So called philosophical foundations of India are declining day to day with the country in a state of social turbulence, the goals and functions of formal education need to be reassessed and updated. Through value based education we can change the world.

1. By giving a place for moral values in the curriculum.
2. Moral values can be explained through stories and illustrations.
3. Through poetry, novel and stories we can inculcate moral values in the students.
4. Role plays of a good story in the lesson.
5. Educate students through posters, advertisements and dramatizations; those are all a part in the curriculum.
6. By introducing a course on moral values as a part of its Master Degree.
7. Giving course training to students to develop moral values in the society.

Teacher as role model,

- Should have a positive, healthy attitude and the right values
- A balanced emotional outlook
- A regulated mind which is able to think clearly and answer without any ambiguity.
- Use and require respectful language
- Encourage student involvement in community service.
- Educate the whole person by focusing on student knowledge, behavior and feeling.

Conclusion:

Value development in children is like growing a plant. In this process, the society, parents, public servants, textbooks, media, and teachers play their respective roles. Among

various entities, the teacher becomes the facilitator to ensure that the value development takes place as per norms. The teacher should always play a proactive role in cultivating the minds of children and developing strong values in them. In this process, let textbooks provide the needed support to the teachers to inspire the young children. Concentrated efforts by all concerned to made to bring about the needed change. Unless efforts and struggle is made the results cannot be seen. So let us as teachers lean to act and not to preach alone.

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